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Synthesis Of Bioactive Molecules Fluoro Substituted Benzothiazole Comprising Potent Heterocyclic Moieties For Biological And Pharmacological Screening

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ABSTRACT

Various 2(5'- substituted phenyl 1',3',4' oxadiazol-2'-yl) amino-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazoles have been synthesized by condensing the compound one with hydrazine hydrate in the presence of ethanol gave the substituted semicarbazide. Further it is refluxed with various substituted aromatic aldehydes in the presence of ethanol. Further, they have been screened for their anthelmintic, anti-inflammatory (*in vivo* and *in vitro*) and anticonvulsant activities.

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Introduction:

The rapid progress of organic Fluorine chemistry¹⁻² since 1950 has been translated as a pathfinder to invent useful biodynamic agents in Medicinal and Biochemistry. The new generation antibiotics like Norfloxacin, Ciproflaxacin, Flufloxacin, which were incorporated with fluorobenzene moiety proved their efficacy as potent bio active molecules. Now a days vast number of compounds with Fluorobenzene³⁻⁵ moiety features in diverse areas like antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, psychoactive agents, pesticides, herbicides etc. The oxadiazole⁶⁻¹⁵ drugs were the first effective chemotherapeutic agents to be employed systematically for the prevention and cure of bacterial infection in human beings. Benzothiazole with oxadiazole group etc. were reported to possess various pharmacological activity of clinical importance. Oxadiazole derivatives are well known to have antimicrobial activities, this also having anti-inflammatory, anthelmintic and anticonvulsant activities.

Materials and methods:

Melting point was determined by open capillary tube method and is uncorrected. T.L.C was run on silica gel G plates using butanol, ethyl acetate and chloroform (1:2:1) as developing solvent for the purity of the compounds. I.R. Spectra were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR Spectrophotometer by using NUJOL MULL technique.

Experimental:**Schiff basis of (1,3) benzothiazoles 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2-semicarbazides :**

2.6 gm of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2-semicarbazide (1,3) benzothiazole was dissolved in absolute alcohol (12.6 ml) then vanilin or benzaldehyde or cinnamaldehyde (0.015 mol) was added. The said above reaction mixture were refluxed for 3 hrs and the excess of solvent removed under reduced pressure, gave Schiff bases of (1,3) benzothiazole 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2-semicarbazides which was recrystallised from alcohol.

Synthesis of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino) (1,3) benzothiazoles:

5.2 gm (0.00132 mol) Schiff bases of (1,3) benzothiazoles 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2-semi carbazides was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and FeCl₃ solution was added with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was shaken for 1 hr and diluted with water (100 ml) then kept at room temperature for 48 hrs. The solid separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol to get 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1',3',4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino) (1,3) benzothiazoles.

Synthesis of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3', 4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino) (1,3) benzothiazoles:

To 0.007 mol of 6-fluoro-7-chloro-2(5'-substituted phenyl) 1', 3',4'oxadiazol-2'-yl amino) (1,3) benzothiazoles was treated with equimolar quantity (0.0075 mol) of various substituted aromatic amines, PABA, morpholine, piperazine, p-toluidine, diphenylamine and n-Methylpiperazine were refluxed for 2 hrs. in the presence of DMF (dimethyl formamide) then the mixture was cooled and poured in to the crushed ice. The solid separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from

benzene and absolute alcohol yield various, 2(5'- substituted phenyl) 1',3',4' oxadiazol-2'-yl amino)-6-fluoro-7-substituted (1,3)-benzothiazoles.

Biological Activities

Anthelmintic activity¹⁶⁻¹⁸:

The synthesized compounds are screened for anthelmintic activity by using earthworms. Six earthworms of nearly equal size were placed in standard drug solution and test compound's solutions at room temperature. Normal saline used as control. The standard drug and test compounds were dissolved in minimum quantity of dimethyl formamide (DMF) and adjusted the volume up to 10 ml with normal saline solution to get the concentration of 0.1 % w/v, 0.2 % w/v and 0.5% w/v. Albendazole was used as a standard drug. The compounds were evaluated by the time taken for complete paralysis and death of earthworms. The mean lethal time for each test compound was recorded and compared with standard drug. The time taken by worms to become motionless was noted as paralysis time. To ascertain the death of the motionless worms were frequently applied with external stimuli, which stimulates and induces movement in the worms, if alive.

Anti-inflammatory activity (*in-vitro* models)¹⁹⁻²²:

The synthesized compounds are screened for anti-inflammatory activity by using inhibition of albumin denaturation technique which was studied according to Muzushima and Kabayashi with slight modification.

Anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenin induced rat hind paw edema method (*in-vivo* model)²³⁻²⁶:

Animals were divided into control, standard, different test groups comprising of five animals in each group. They were fasted overnight with free access to water before experiment. In all groups, acute inflammation was produced by subplanter injection of 0.1 ml of freshly prepared 1% suspension of carrageenin in the right hind paw of the rats and paw volume was measured plethysmometrically at 0 hr and 3 hrs after carrageenin injection. The test compounds (50 mg/kg) was administered orally, standard group was treated with diclofenac (50 mg/kg) orally 1 hr. before by injection and control group received only vehicle. Mean difference in paw volume was measured and percentage inhibition was calculated by following formula.

$$\% \text{ inhibition of edema} = \left[\frac{V_c - V_t}{V_c} \right] \times 100$$

Where, V_t = mean paw volume of test group.

V_c = mean paw volume of control group.

Anticonvulsant activity²⁷⁻²⁹:

In the present study the mice of either sex, weighing between 20-25 g were selected and divided into control, test and standard. Before experiment the animal were fasted for 24 hrs with only water *ad-libitum*. Control group received only 0.5 ml DMF as vehicle. Standard group animals were received diazepam (4 mg/kg b.w.) oral test group animals were received the synthesized derivatives at 4 mg/kg b.w. oral in DMF. Now for the animals of control group pentylene tetrazole (PTZ) 1ml/100 g b.w. was administered and actions like stratubs tail, jerky movements of whole body and convulsions were observed. For animals of standard test group PTZ was injected (1 ml/100 g body weight). After 30 min animals of standard and test received diazepam and synthesized derivatives respectively

Results and Discussion:

Anthelmintic activity : Synthesized compounds were tested for anthelmintic activity. The compounds V₁, to V₁₂, B₁, B₂, B₃, B₄, B₅, B₆, B₇, C₂, C₄, C₅, C₆, C₉, C₁₀, and C₁₁, showed significant paralytic time of earthworms compared to standard **Albendazole** of 0.1, 0.2, 0.5% concentrations of compounds, showed comparatively better death time of earthworms with that of standard drug. After all, the synthesized compounds in overall estimation confirms the better activity against (*perituma posthuma*).

1) Anti-inflammatory activity (*in-vitro*):

The compounds V₁, V₂, V₉, B₁, B₃, B₆, C₁, C₂, and C₉, showed significant antiinflammatory activity compare to standard **Ibuprofen** (93.87%).

2) Anti-inflammatory activity (*In-vivo* models) :

The compounds were tested for anti-inflammatory activity by invivo method compared to standard Diclofenac Sodium.

The compounds V₃, V₄, V₅, V₁₁, V₁₂, B₁, B₅, B₇, B₉, B₁₀, C₃, C₄, C₅, C₁₁, and C₁₂, showed significant anti-inflammatory activity compare to standard drug **Diclofenac Sodium** (79.60%).

3) Anticonvulsant activity :

synthesized compounds were tested for anticonvulsant activity by PTZ (pentylene tetrazole) induced method **Diazepam** used as standard drug.

From the anticonvulsant activity observation the compounds V₁, V₄, V₅, V₈, V₁₁, B₁, B₅, B₆, B₈, B₁₀, B₁₁, C₂, C₄, C₆, C₈ and C₁₀ have shown significant anti- anticonvulsant activity.

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SCHEME

References:

1. Feller R.J. Fluorine Chem 1995; 33: 366.
2. Greco Micheal N, Hangman William E. Chem Abstr 1992; 117; 131109 z.
3. Sutoris V. Chem Abstr 1991; 10683584 f.
4. Wollesdrof OW Jr, Schwam H. Chem Abstr 1989; 111: 194656 x.
5. Scholewald, Ronald D. Chem Abstr 1984; 1002069678 c.
6. Nailesh Joshi, Sushil Korgaokar and Hansa Prekh. Ind J Heter Chem 1996; 5: 241-242.
7. Balakrishna Kalluraya, Ramesh Chimbalkar, Prashantha Gunaga. Ind J Hetero Chem 1996; 6: 103-106.
8. Dharmveer Singh, Atma Ram Mishra, Rakesh Mai Mishra. Ind J Hetero Chem 2005; 14: 289-292.
9. Mohd Afroz Bakht, Mojahidul Islam, Anees A Siddiqui. Ind J Hetero Chem 2006; 15: 297-298.
10. Bhaskar VH, Prashanth Francis, Sangameswaram B. Ind J Hetero Chem 2006; 15: 409-410.
11. Alagawadi KR, Mahajanshetti CS, Jalalpure SS. Ind J Hetero Chem 2005; 14: 315-318.
12. Dutta MM, Katakya JCS. Ind J Hetero Chem 1996; 6: 59-62.
13. Nirmala Sidker, Bulakh NR, Mehilal, Sikdar AK. Ind J Hetero Chem 2002; 12: 29-32.
14. Khan MSY, Khan RM, Sushmadrabhu. Ind J Hetero Chem 2001; 11: 119-122.
15. Shivaram Holla B, Narayana Poojary, Subramanya Bhat K. Ind J Chem 2005; 44B: 1669-1673.
16. Bushan Kumar S Sathe, Sreenivasa GM, Jayachandran E, Sreenivasa Rao D and Nargund LVG, Int J Chem Sci 2006; 4(3); 545-552.
17. Sreenivas GM, Shivakumar B, Rao SD and Jayachandra E, Ind Drugs 2006; 43(4).
18. Jayachandran E, Bhatia K, Nargund LVG and Roy A. Ind Drugs 2003; 40(7).
19. Srinivasa GM, Jayachandra E, Shivakumar B, Sreenivasa Rao D. Oriental J Chem 2004; 20(1); 103-110.
20. Gelios, Rao MNA. Ind J Exp Biol 1998; 26.
21. Sreenivas Rao D, Jayachandra E, Sreenivasa GM and Shivakumar B, Oriental J Chem 2005; 21(1): 113-116.

22. Hitendra Yadav, Sreenivasa GM, Jayachandran and Kore Srinivasa. J Ultra Chem 2006; 2(1): 7-16.
23. Nagendra Rao R, Jayachandran E, Sreenivasa GM and Jyothi TM. Ori J Chem 2005; 21(2): 327-330.
24. Sreenivasa GM, Jayachandra E and Shivakumar B. Ind J Hetro Chem 2004; 14: 89-90.
25. Khan MSY, Khan RM, Sushmadrabhu. Ind J Hetero Chem 2001; 11: 119-122.
26. Abdel Ghany aly el-helby, Mohammed Hemeda abdel wahed. Acta Pharm 2003; 53: 127-138.
27. Turner RA. Anti-epileptic drugs, in screening methods in pharmacology, 15th ed.(Ed. R.A. Turner), Academic Press, New York 1965; 165-172.
28. Khan MSY, Khan RM, Sushmadrabhu. Ind J Hetero Chem 2001; 11: 119-122.
29. Abdel Ghany aly el-helby, Mohammed Hemeda abdel wahed. Acta Pharm 2003; 53: 127-138.

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